

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Statistical approach to defect simulation in complex analog and mixed-signal circuits: application to radiation-induced single-event transients</i>
Project TA identifier	TA03-04
General application	Space
Type of test	SEE (Heavy Ions)
Group leader, Institute	Gildas Leger, Instituto de Microelectrónica de Sevilla (IMSE-CNM, CSIC, Universidad de Sevilla)
Date of the experiment	March 30 th , 2023
Facility	GANIL (Caen, France)
Amount of access granted	8 hours

Objectives of the experiments

This project draws a parallelism between fabrication defect detection and SET detection in Analog, Mixed-Signal and RF systems. Indeed, both are stochastic processes that can affect any device in the system with different likelihood, related to the geometry. Most fabrication defects arise from impurity particles landing on the wafer at any of the lithography steps. On the other hand, SET arises from ionizing particles hitting sensitive circuit areas.

In both cases, designers want to assess the sensitivity of their system (to either defect or SET) before fabrication, and simulation is thus mandatory. Unfortunately, large systems offer too many defect/SET candidates for an exhaustive simulation to be feasible. Statistical approaches with simplified models are thus mandatory.

Scientifically validating these approximations is impossible for fabrication defects, since these are scarce and it would thus be necessary to have access to volume fabrication data, which is one of the best-guarded secrets from foundries. However, many different SETs can be generated for a single circuit. In this project, we thus want to radiate a purposely designed prototype and compare the relative sensitivity of different regions/blocks to what can be obtained by statistical electrical simulations with different levels of approximation and sampling schemes.

We thus built a complex mixed-signal demonstrator to try to answer the following questions:

- 1) Which SET injection model, among different approximations, best matches the experimental results in terms of sensitivities?
- 2) Does our statistical approach match the experimental confidence intervals?
- 3) Are the SET detectors embedded on the rad-hard channel efficient?
- 4) Does conversion redundancy help radiation hardness?
- 5) How does the demonstrator behave with respect to SEE?

Experiment test report

Description of the demonstrator:

Since we aimed at a system-level simulation methodology, the demonstrator was a complex mixed-signal circuit: a 2-channel Successive Approximation Register Analog-to-Digital Converter (SAR-ADC). These converters have been designed in a TSMC 65 nm CMOS technology and are radiation-hardened by design.

The nominal supply voltage for the ASIC core is 1.2 V, while the pad ring and the digital IO buffers are biased at 2.5 V. The silicon die of the ASIC has an area of 4 mm².

The converters implement 3 bits of redundancy, using 16 internal comparisons to output 13 bits of resolution. They can operate up to 40 MSa/s, but for the radiation campaign, the sampling clock was reduced to 20 MHz.

The converters are also equipped with a foreground self-calibration machine to reduce the impact of capacitor mismatching and comparator offset and to digitally cancel the global offset of each channel. The digital reconstruction engine in the digital section of the ASIC takes into account the redundancy and the calibration registers to provide the 13 bits output word. 3 additional bits are used to carry relevant information from the internal chip sensors, synchronously to the output data. This forms a 16 bits output word which is sent to 8 output pins in a DDR format.

In addition to these 3 additional bits, two dedicated digital test pins can be programmed to output more internal flags.

The chip also includes a high-performance reference generator that makes use of an internal bandgap.

The digital section, which includes the calibration engine, the reconstruction engine, the DDR module, and the SPI communication module to the different configuration registers, has been designed using the DARE library of rad-hard logic gates from IMEC.

In addition, SET detectors of two classes were also embedded in the circuit:

- A window detector that aims at detecting SET pulses on internal DC signals. The window is digitally tunable and the DC node to be monitored can be selected through a multiplexer.
- A couple of assertion detectors in one of the SAR channels concurrently check the integrity of internal signals. Namely, one computes the average of the differential comparator input and compares it to the common-mode voltage. The other checks that the value of the conversion residue (i.e., the differential value at the comparator input at the end of the successive approximation cycles) is below a certain (programmable) value. Indeed, whatever the linearity of the converter, the conversion residue should always be below 1 LSB.

The ADCs have been electrically characterized prior to the radiation campaign. They show a very good performance, maintaining an Effective Number Of Bits (ENOB) above 11 over the military temperature range, with a maximum of around 12 bits, for a sampling frequency up to 35 MHz.

Description of the test platform:

The ASIC has been soldered directly onto a PCB to maximize performance.

<https://radnext.web.cern.ch/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/radnext>

All the data acquisition and board control were performed in the digital domain using an FPGA. This FPGA was interfaced through a USB connection to a local PC in the radiation chamber, which itself was remotely controlled through Ethernet from the control room. The FPGA also controlled the 16 bits low-frequency DACs that generated the differential input voltage to the ADCs. As well, a power monitoring and disconnection scheme was implemented to protect the ASIC from SEL, as seen in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 SEL protection scheme

The monitoring involved two ADCs for the two power domains (the 2.5 V for the IOs in the pad-ring, and the 1.2 V for the ASIC core). Their outputs were fed to the FPGA which controlled the disconnection switches. Such a setup allows setting different current thresholds as a function of the ASIC operating mode and board conditions. Indeed, the power-on-reset sequence of the ASIC sets the chip in a default configuration that is not the same as the radiation configuration. The implemented algorithm, depicted in Fig. 2, automatically restores the correct configuration after a programmable time, by addressing the ASIC SPI interface. In the meantime, a different current threshold is used for the purpose of latchup detection.

Fig. 1 SEL protection algorithm

A dedicated application in Python was developed to store the data from the radiation campaign in a database and control the platform.

Test description:

Our test plan consisted of submitting the circuit to high fluxes at different LET values and in different configurations to compare the obtained results with those obtained by simulation.

The baseline configuration consisted in having the two channels operating concurrently, both with the same DC input, and the DC SET detector connected to a reasonably quiet internal node of the reference generator.

The following events were considered for SET detection:

- Single-Event-Latchup is detected upon an increase of the current consumption (done at board level)
- The ADC output exits the acceptable code window for the DC level (either up or down).
- The DC SET detector gives a positive output (either up or down the detection window)
- The embedded assertion detectors give a positive output
- The two channels outputs differ for more than a given threshold

Upon any detection (except the SEL which triggers a power reset cycle), the chip status register was read, giving access to additional information about the integrity of the configuration registers, so that we can discard SEUs in the digital section.

For each detection event, we store:

- The value of all the detection flags
- The ADC output at the trigger instant
- The value of the two power monitors at the trigger instant
- The timestamp of the SEE detection
- The timestamp of the SEE end
- The maximum deviation from the expected DC value over this time range
- The ASIC status register

Preliminary results:

Figure 4 shows the ADC error code for a ramp input corresponding to the acquisitions quoted in Fig. 3. The legend is in chronological order from top to bottom. The full-range figure shows that under radiation, we are able to capture some single events that manifest as sharp peaks in the transfer function. In the zoom-in, however, we can appreciate how the code error follows a common trend, which shows that the Integral Non-Linearity (INL) of the converter is not affected by the dose.

Fig. 4 ADC output code error for an input ramp a) full-scale b) zoom-in

Table 1 shows the SETs detected for the golden configuration under different LETs. Notice that these are the total number of Single Events Effects, whatever their nature. However, thanks to our database

structure, we can further classify them according to the root cause(s).

LET (MeV.cm ² /mg)	Flux (p/cm ² /s)	Duration (s)	#SETs	99% Confidence Interval
27.03	9503	604	77	[56;98]
41.35	8661	626	1173	[1091;1270]
51.58	8111	606	1062	[975;1143]
64.18	10849	838	1973	[1865;2078]

According to this table, the saturated cross-section for this SET definition is around 0.022 mm², to be compared to the 4 mm² die area.

Noticeably, we did not register any latchup during the entire radiation campaign. This is not surprising since the ASIC was radiation-hardened by design.

Over the entire radiation time, we only registered a couple of events that did disrupt the operation, but could be recovered by reprogramming the ASIC. In view of the circuit response, we think that these events correspond to impacts in the Power-on-Reset circuitry, which caused an undue reset of the chip.

With respect to the digital section, we have identified a total number of 16 SEUs (i.e., undue bitflips in the configuration registers) over the complete duration of the experiment for the 848 Flip-Flops that were monitored. None of these SEUs, however, impacted the circuit operation so they probably correspond to some non-critical fields. Figure 5 shows the calculated cross-section as a function of the LET:

Fig.5 FF cross-section for the monitored registers

Preliminary comments on the Experiment objectives

- 1) Which SET injection model, among different approximations, best matches the experimental results in terms of sensitivities?

When we compare the relative cross-sections over different configurations, LETs and/or SET definitions, with the relative sensitivities obtained by simulation, the preliminary results indicate

that there is no good matching. The most accurate transistor-level model gives the closest results, but still does not match all the observed trends. This seems to indicate that some relevant effects remain unmodeled at the system level. This is a very interesting result that will trigger further research. We will have to do complementary experiments/simulations to get a better understanding of the underlying unmodeled phenomena.

- 2) Does our statistical approach match the experimental confidence intervals?

This question cannot be correctly answered since the bias error (due to the unmodeled effects) is larger than the variability.

- 3) Are the SET detectors embedded on the rad-hard channel efficient?

The assertion detectors were able to detect SETs that do not cause a significant variation in the output of the ADC, so the detectors exhibit great sensitivity. However, some SETs that did affect the ADC output were not caught by the assertion detectors. This could be expected since some events can occur in the signal flow past the detectors, for instance in the digital buffers of the output word. The detectors are thus working quite well.

- 4) Does conversion redundancy help radiation hardness?

The distribution of the SET at the ADC output shows a contained impact both in terms of amplitude and peak duration. It is difficult to relate this good behavior only to redundancy. Indeed, the experimental data seem to indicate that the SAR conversion process itself is not directly affected by ion impacts. Most of the SETs seem to be caused by the reference and bias generator. This very good behavior of the differential signal path points out that the redundancy is effective. However, a conclusive experiment would require implementing another ADC without redundancy.

- 5) How does the demonstrator behave with respect to SEE?

The ADCs have exhibited very few issues even under large LET, with most output peaks well below full-scale excursion.

The ASIC is latchup-free up to a LET of 64 MeV.cm²/mg at room temperature and exhibited very few SEUs.

These are very encouraging results in terms of radiation hardness.

With respect to the SEE simulation framework, the results are not those that we hoped, but they will give us an opportunity to better understand the impact of radiation on complex mixed-signal systems. We thus consider it a relevant result.

With respect to the ADC radiation-hardness performance, the results are extremely encouraging and the part seems to be in the state-of-the-art.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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